

Svitlana Dombrovska**Head of the educational-scientific-production center
of the National University of Civil Defence of Ukraine****Doctor of Sciences (Public Administration), Full Professor****ORCID: 0000-0002-8627-0057****TO THE QUESTION OF MECHANISMS OF STATE REGULATION OF THE
HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UKRAINE****(DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3625574)**

The country's transition to a market economy necessitates the reform of higher education, which would fully assist the formation of independent thinking of the individual, strengthen an individual approach to the development of creative abilities, radically improve the professional training of specialists who are able to work in new conditions. The article shows the results of studies of the processes of reforming higher education in Ukraine, analyzes world statistics, regulatory documents that govern the formation of the educational space.

Keywords: higher education, educational reform, higher educational institutions.

Mankind is entering a new century with enormous scientific and technical achievements that change the way people think about the world and their place in it. Electronic information systems allow the five billion people of the planet to not only instantly hear about events in its various countries, but also to see them. Under these conditions, the spatiotemporal framework of a person's being expands immeasurably, his worldview is transformed; he begins to think in categories that reflect the global nature of his life. The concepts of "world civilization", "world culture", "universal values" and others constantly appear in the media, are widely used in scientific discussions and in legislative acts.

In recent years, the phrase “educational space” has become very popular in pedagogical treatises, which is used to describe the educational situation in the world and its regions. In the real sprouts of integration in the field of education one can see an already forming single world educational space, which is guided by a “world educational policy” that sets the main goals for countries, common approaches to the content, methods and teaching aids, providing an exchange of educational services. After gaining independence in 1991, Ukraine began to formulate and implement its own policy in the field of higher education, aimed at achieving a modern level of quality and accessibility, reviving original national traditions, fundamentally updating the content, forms and methods of training, organizational foundations of activity, enhancing the intellectual potential of Ukraine.

Ukraine inherited from previous times a rather developed and widely ramified system of higher education, which in many respects corresponds to the level of developed countries of the world.

The conceptual foundations of its reform were determined by the State National Program “Education. Ukraine in 21st century.”

The implementation of the program provided for the achievement of a qualitatively new state of higher education, its integration into the international educational space. The program defines ways to ensure the priority development of education in Ukraine, attracting all state and public institutions, private structures to active participation in this process. One of the most important tasks is the orientation of higher education to meet the educational needs of each person, taking into account national cultural rights and the needs of all citizens of the country, regardless of their ethnicity. This was realized, first of all, through updating the content of education, its mutual coordination at all educational levels, the introduction of advanced pedagogical concepts and technologies, taking into account the best domestic and world experience, the formation of a new generation of teaching staff. One of the areas of reform is overcoming the state monopoly in the field of higher education, ensuring its

multistructure and diversification of educational programs, creating a variety of sources of financing, improving and democratizing forms of governance, and creating educational institutions of various types.

The main directions of state policy in the field of higher education are determined by the Constitution of Ukraine, the laws of Ukraine "On Education" and "On Higher Education", acts of the President of Ukraine and the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. The Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education" regulates public relations in the field of education, training, and vocational training of citizens of Ukraine. The results of the development of the national higher education system for ten years of independence of Ukraine were analyzed at the II All-Ukrainian Congress of Education Workers (2001), the further strategy of the development of the system is defined in the National Doctrine of Education Development - a state document that defines a system of views on the strategy and main directions of education in Ukraine the first quarter of the XXI century.

Accordingly, the Doctrine of education serves as the basis for the development of the individual, society, nation and state, a guarantee of the future of Ukraine. The state is gradually increasing spending on education and brings them to the average of the countries of the European Union, but not less than 10 percent of GDP. The effectiveness of the use of financial resources allocated to education is ensured on the basis of the establishment and steady observance of the basic principles of its financing:

- a gradual transition to the formation of state and local budgets in the field of education based on established standards per student;
- a clear delineation of the use of budgetary and extrabudgetary funding of educational institutions;
- the introduction of a direct relationship between the amount of funding and the level of educational services provided by a particular institution;

In the context of globalization processes in the world, the creation of a single educational space, the strategic task of state educational policy is to

enter Ukrainian education on the world educational services market, deepen international cooperation, expand the participation of educational institutions, teachers, students and researchers in projects of international organizations and communities. The state assists in the development of cooperation between educational institutions on a bilateral and multilateral basis with intergovernmental and non-governmental international organizations and institutions (UNESCO, UNICEF, the European Union, the Council of Europe), the World Bank, foreign educational funds, and other international organizations.

The integration of Ukraine's education in the international educational space is based on the principles of priority of national interests, preservation and development of the intellectual potential of the nation, peacekeeping and creative orientation of international cooperation, orientation to national, European and universal fundamental values, developing, systematic and mutually beneficial nature of cooperation and tolerance in assessing and perception of foreign education systems.

One of the main system-forming features of higher education in Ukraine is professional qualification as a result of citizens getting higher education.

The structure and form of the higher education system of Ukraine, as well as most countries that emerged after the collapse of the USSR, is characterized by the simultaneous receipt of academic (educational) and professional qualifications - professional higher education.

For any level of education, a professional or academic (educational) qualification can be determined, acquired by citizens simultaneously during the implementation of the corresponding educational and professional program of a certain educational qualification level and the corresponding educational level. Their acquisition is confirmed by a diploma - a document on higher education, which is both a certificate and, in most cases, a license.

Thus, in Ukraine there is a harmonious combination of a two-stage structure of higher academic education that meets the basic and complete

levels of higher education and professional training. Without exaggeration, this organic association is the greatest asset of the national higher education system, a guarantee of its adaptation to the changing socio-economic realities and needs of society in the long term and in the broad sense, as well as to the development of a new model of education - lifelong education.

The management of the higher education industry is defined by the Legislation of Ukraine on Higher Education and is based on the Constitution of Ukraine and consists of: Laws of Ukraine "On Education", "On Higher Education", "On Scientific and Scientific-Technical Activities".

Accordingly, the National Doctrine of the Development of Education, the modern education management system is approved as a state-public. It can take into account regional peculiarities, growth trends in the autonomy of educational institutions, the competitiveness of educational services, and the orientation of education not toward reproduction, but toward personality development. The higher education sector in Ukraine is managed by the Cabinet of Ministers (Government of Ukraine) through the system of executive bodies (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine) and other central executive bodies to which higher education institutions are subordinate.

Given the requirements for the level of professional training in the context of Ukraine's integration into the global system of training, certification and certification of specialists, one of the most important tasks is the creation of a state-public system of social guarantees. It will also provide an opportunity to fulfill the requirements of the Lisbon Agreement regarding state guarantees of the quality of education.

Along with such important components of quality assurance as the careful selection of teachers and administrators and the continuous improvement of their qualifications, the development of new technologies and teaching methods, the integration of educational and scientific components of the educational institution, it is extremely important to constantly monitor the effectiveness of the educational process.

The main tools capable of providing both internal and external assessment at the national and international levels, while maintaining respect for the autonomy of the institution and its academic freedoms, is the mechanism for licensing and accrediting educational activities of both the institution itself and training programs. Monitoring of compliance with the License conditions within the framework of their authority is carried out by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, educational authorities of regions, the State Inspectorate of educational institutions by conducting scheduled and unscheduled inspections. Based on the results of the audit, the governing body may decide to revoke the license for educational activities. Decisions of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine on licensing issues may be appealed in court. Accreditation of a direction or specialty of a certain direction is a state recognition of the conformity of the level of training (retraining) of specialists in areas or specialties with state requirements.

Only accredited higher education institutions have the right to issue documents on higher education recognized by the state.

In accordance with the current regulatory and regulatory and methodological documents, Ukraine uses educational technologies inherent in the system of higher professional education.

Given that professional qualifications are always specific, and professional training in a higher educational institution has significant resource limitations (especially in time), professional higher education in Ukraine is aimed at preparing a person to fulfill the duties and tasks (professional work) of a certain position (or positions)) The vast majority of positions defined by industry qualification guides require significant practical experience of professional activity (professional experience) from a specialist. Therefore, vocational training is “tuned” to a limited number of positions that do not require previous practical experience from graduates of the educational institution — the so-called primary positions. The academic qualification of graduates allows them to further pursue a professional career through the acquisition of a certain

practical experience (competency), or by changing qualifications in postgraduate education institutions and other institutions intended for this purpose. In the vocational education system of Ukraine, the primary positions for each qualification are for the most part determined by one of the main regulatory documents of the sphere of labor and social protection - the Directory of qualification characteristics of professions, job descriptions, that is, lists of tasks and responsibilities that employees must fulfill, requirements for their professional knowledge, educational and qualification levels. Fundamentally new to the updated system of higher education in Ukraine is the expansion of the student's ability to choose the specialty that he wants to receive after completing training in a certain direction. Previously, this specialty was already recorded when entering a higher educational institution, and it was rather difficult to change it. In the system of step-by-step education, a student after 3-4 years of study can choose one of several specialties proposed by the standard (training programs) according to his tastes or the situation on the labor market, which can be more clearly predicted for 1 or 2 years in advance. Previously, he chose a specialty 5 years before graduating from a higher educational institution, without actually knowing the market prospects.

Thus, the system of normative and methodological documents regulating the activities of the higher education system of Ukraine, in terms of structure and composition and while maintaining a certain level of state regulation of activities in the field of higher education, makes it possible to ensure the autonomy and academic independence of higher education institutions, more in line with the educational qualification level of training specialists requirements of the social division of labor in Ukraine, mobility of the training specialist respect to meet labor market requirements and, most importantly - free personality development of students according to their inclinations and preferences.

Higher education standards are developed taking into account the European level of requirements for higher education, which will contribute to a

more complete entry of Ukraine into the global educational space. In the standards, the humanistic direction of higher education is particularly reflected. In particular, they establish the normative part of the content of education, which ensures the compulsory study of social and humanitarian disciplines: law, philosophy, ethics, aesthetics, world and domestic culture, etc. Disciplines of a humanistic, ethnographic nature make up about 20% of the training time for training specialists. In addition, the standards of higher education provide for the humanistic orientation of fundamental and special educational disciplines. Standards provide not only the European level of formation of education and the development of professional skills, but also the upbringing of a harmoniously developed, socially active tolerant person with high spiritual qualities, capable of self-development and self-improvement.

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